

Unearthing the Agrarian Debate in The R̥g Veda

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Ankit Sharma

Research Scholar
History Department
Panjab University
Chandigarh, India

Abstract Over the period, the notion of the Rig Vedic agrarian economy has been a subject of intense debate among historians and scholars. The riddle of the original home of Aryans has further complicated it. It has been argued that they came to India from outside and carried out their traditional nomadic life till they didn't occupy the *Gangatic* region. The historians with their preconceived notion presumed that the same Aryan society occupied the area of *Sapta-Sindhu* and composed Rig Veda. Historians like D. D. Kosambi, and R. S. Sharma popularise the notion that Rig Vedic Aryans were semi-nomadic and society was primarily pastoral. The main argument is that the Rig Veda contains a plethora of references for cattle, especially of cow and the nomenclature is mainly the extension of the word 'Go'. Besides that Indra who was the god of war praises more than other gods. The paper aims to raise certain questions regarding this statistical approach and by challenging prevailing notions, it seeks to broaden our understanding of the Rig Vedic economy and encourage new ways of examining this ancient text.

Keywords R̥g Veda, Indra, Aryans, Agrarian, Nomadic.

Introduction

V. A. Smith was the 1st who structured the image of R̥g Vedic pastoral-nomadic.[1] The theory was popularized by Indian Marxist historians like D. D. Kosambi, R. S. Sharma, and D. N. Jha. The paper is seeking to question the arguments of this popular and established narrative.

The narrative of pastoral-dominated society in the Rig Veda is mainly based upon the following factors emphasized by various scholars: -

1. Plethora of references for cattle especially for cow
2. *Indra* as war god who leads the army in the battle
3. Scarcity of agricultural references

According to Kosambi,[2] RV frequently mentions the cattle, especially of cows which shows that they were possibly pastoral society. Later on, R. S. Sharma popularized this view by including some more facts in it. He says that *Rayi*, which mentions in RV, was the synonym for cattle wealth.[3] To strengthen his argument he gives certain statistical data. He argues that the terms like *Jana* (275), *Vis* (170), *Gana*, *Vrāta* repeatedly occur which implies the tribal structure of R̥g Vedic people.[4] The term *Pasu* was used for mainly domesticated cattle which were explicitly valued for non-vegetarian food and dairy products.[5] He further says that in the family mandala cow occurs 176 times in different declensions and argues that the significance of cow is indicated by the use of the term *duhitr* (one who milks) for daughter.[6] D. N. Jha argues that the terms like *Gopa* or *Gopati*, *Gomat*, *Duhitr*, *Gavya* *Gaviṣṭi* show the pastoral basis of the economy of R̥g Vedic Aryans which they inherited from their Indo-European past.[7]

Before taking this narrative as a fact it would be conducive to getting aware of certain other facts that historians knowingly and intentionally don't highlight. The R̥g *Samhita* as it stands today represents only those portions that a particular school decided to preserve and there are names of authors of hymns and not of the editor(s).[8] The RV is concerned more with ritual and natural phenomena than human habitation.[9] RV is ultimately poetry where there is wide room for the poetical license.[10] But the historians especially R. S. Sharma who popularized and established this theory of pastoral-predominated society in the RV, give more importance to statistical data rather than realizing the contextual importance of it.

- Objective of study**
1. To explore the extensive references to cattle, particularly cows, in the context of the study.
 2. To analyze the depiction of Indra as a war god leading the army in battles.
 3. To investigate the relative scarcity of references to agriculture within the studied texts.

Review of Literature

The contextual study is important since the Ṛg Vedic hymns and verses are composed in the form of simile and metaphor where they are comparing two things simultaneously. For example the term 'Go' and terms which are associated with it are frequently mentioned in the RV. E. Hopkins challenges the notion of taking cows in its real sense every time. He quotes certain verses to prove that many times cow uses in a metaphorical sense.[11] P. V. Pathak interprets the term 'Go' as a segment of land that submerges under water behind the *Vṛtra*, the earthen bund.[12] Besides that G. Wojtilla interprets the term as ox used for ploughing.[13] Most scholars interpret the term '*Goviṣṭi*' as the war for the cow. S. A. Dange makes an interesting interpretation of this term. According to him the term *Goviṣṭi* compound of two words 'Go' and *isti* and the term 'Go' means the welfare of the cow. So the possibility of war for cows in any way is not possible. To buttress his argument he says that *Goviṣṭi* is never mentioned in the context of *Panīs*, who stole cows.[14] Taking textual evidence too literally one could conclude as a remark by A. B. Keith[15] that the original Indo-European knows butter but not milk; snow and feet and not rain and hand.

Main Text

Most of historians believe that *Indra* was the most important god of RV since it occurs 250 times. He was the god of war who leads the army in the battlefield. But the detailed study of Rig Vedic hymns and verses implies that *Indra* was also the rain god and this fact is merely highlighted by historians or less importance given to it. The question arises here why *Indra*, who was the predominant god of Rig Vedic people, the god of rain, is why consistent prayers are being offered for him.

A. C. Das[16] makes an interesting observation that scanty rain with long draught and barren clouds, often presented the ideal weather to the pastoral for pasturing their cattle and roaming about from place to place whereas agricultural populations on the other hand were in dire need of copious rain. The situation for the latter one seems more pertinent when we study the *Indra-Vṛtra* mythological war in which *Vṛtra* is identified with the obstacle of water.[17]

The theme of Rig Vedic mythology mainly revolved around the *Indra-Vṛtra* war. The term *Vṛtra* means obstruction or resistance.[18] According to Griswold[19], the genesis of every demon may be traced back to some painful and bad experience, for instance, the experience of drought, disease, or cold. Prof. Muir believes that the conception of demons was "an idea quite in consonance with the other general conceptions, which their authors entertained, to imagine that some malignant influence was at work in the atmosphere to prevent the fall of the showers." [20] At this point, it would be pertinent to raise certain questions. Why did the Ṛg Vedic poets choose this theme *Indra-Vṛtra* war? Is there any historical significance in this mythical war? Were the rain and rivers praised for the good yield of crops?

In RV, it is not only *Indra* who praise rain but other gods too. The *Parjanya* is also the god of rain.[21] There are many hymns and verses where Maruts pray for rain.[22] Interestingly other gods are praised for rain. *Agni* is praised as the giver of rain and abundant food.[23] If we make a comprehensive and intensive study of RV, then it becomes evident that there are not only these prominent gods who are praised for shedding rain but almost all Ṛg Vedic pantheons are praying for rain and water. *Ashwins*, the twin gods, are also praying for rain. The passage goes like Ashwin giver of rain and protector of men.[24] *Brihaspati* refers to the sender of rain and the giver of food and *Viśas* (people).[25] *Ribhus* is a promoter of rain and the flow of water to low places to promote good works.[26] *Adityas* who are the sons of *Aditi*, the mother goddess, are all praised for rain. The *Adityas*, call the collector of rain, acquitters of debt, and upholders of movable and immovable things.[27]

There is another important facet of *Vṛtra* that most scholars ignored. It is not only *Indra* who is fighting with *Vṛtra* but the other gods too. There are numerous hymns where *Agni* fights with *Vṛtra* and killed him eventually.[28] Besides that other gods also combating with *Vṛtra*. [29] It clearly shows that they are fighting with a common enemy. *Kosambi* believes that the demons whom *Indra* killed such as *Śambara*, *Pipru*, *Arśasānas*, *Śusna* were the personification of drought.[30] This assumption seems to be correct except in the case of *Śambara* who is referred to as the owner of cattle and *Divodasa* defeats him by winning over the cattle.[31] The demon *Arbuda* is also interpreted as a demon of drought.[32] A. Lahiri also identified demons such as *Vṛtra*, *Śusna*, *Kuvaya*, and *Aṣṇa* as demons of drought which he concludes that Aryans were dependent on rain for their agriculture.[33] It seems, from the above mention facts, that the poets and the people to whom they are praying were in dire need of rain and water.

Now the question arises if Aryans were nomadic and pastoral then why they frequently prayed for rain? The Rg Vedic people whether Aryan or non-Aryans fight with each other frequently. R. S. Sharma believes that since they are pastoral and nomadic people (Aryans) fight only for cattle. But why then they are praying for rain and most of the gods fighting with demons for releasing rain and water? Kosambi made an interesting statement about the Ten-Kings battle. According, to him, the ten kings tried to divert the course of *Parushni* (modern name Ravi) river.[34] Can it say that these ten kings and *Sudasa*, the Bharata king, fought for the water which might be used for irrigation purposes? Surely nothing can be said but the possibility can't be rooted out. *Jataka* traditions mention the famous battle between *Sakya* and *Koliya* tribes over the river water of *Rohini* which they used for their irrigation purpose. These two tribes lived on opposite banks of the river *Rohini*. The *Sakya* tribe lived in a village that was surrounded by rice fields.[35] The same pattern of living might be followed by the Rg Vedic Aryans which forced them to fight for the cause of water. There is an important passage from RV that buttress this argument. It goes as:

अहमत्कं कवये शिश् नथं हथैरहं कुत्समावमभिरुतिभिः ।

अहं शुष्णस्य श्रयिता वधर्यम न यो रर आर्यं नाम दस्यवे ||[36]

The passage goes as I (Indra) smote Atka with many weapons for the defense of the sage: with those protections I preserved Kutsa; I am the slayer of Śuṣṇa: I grasped the thunderbolt I who have not given the water of the Aryan to the Dasyu.

In the mythical war, Indra contests *Vṛtra* with his thunderbolt to get victorious and release the water. As we have discussed above that *Vṛtra* is interpreted in two different ways. He is either identified with a cloud that restrains water in the sky or a long drought caused by scanty rain. Could it be a real war that Rg Vedic people are fighting for? Kosambi identified the killing of *Vṛtra* with the destruction of the artificial dam that ultimately ruined Indus agriculture.[37]It seems that author somewhere is subscribing the M. Wheeler's Aryan Invasion theory. But he is somewhere contradicting his argument since he identified Indra as the rain god. How, a god who is praying for rain, can destroy the artificial dam that he identified with *Vṛtra*. S. Piggott makes an interesting observation by citing one Rg Vedic verses. He says that in the same hymn in which *Indra* is describing its celestial character realizing rain swelling rivers and praying for flood and conquest simultaneously.[38]There are numerous hymns where Indra is praying for rain and fought with *Vṛtra*. [39]It clearly shows that *Vṛtra* is not the one identified by Kosambi.

So, then who was the *Vṛtra* and was he a historical figure or only a mythical character? Before, excepting any of the views it is very important to get aware of a few more evidences. As mentioned above, in RV, *Indra* is not only fighting for water with *Vṛtra* but also with other enemies like *Ahi*, *Śusna*, *Arbuda*, etc...[40] The term *Dāsa* which historians identified with aboriginal and called the enemy of Aryans also falls in that category where *Indra* fought with him for water. The passage goes like this:

यः सृबिन्दमनर्शनिं पिपुं दासमहिशुवम् |वधीदुगो रिणन्नपः ||[41]

The fierce (deity) who, liberating the waters, has slain *Sṛbinda*, *Anarśani*, *Pipru*, and the slave *Ahiśuva*. *Sāyaṇa* identified the phrase 'Dasam ca ahiśuvam ca' as the proper name of *Dāsa*. Griffith[27] interpreted the verse as "Strong god, he slays *Anarśani*, *Sṛbinda*, *Pipru*, and the slave *Ahiśuva*, and loses the floods. He says that all the names mentioned in the verse are the name of drought. Besides that *Dāsas* also refer as the master of water.[42]

If, the above discussion, where we see that it's not only the *Vṛtra* but other enemies or demons also identified with drought or who obstruct rain or water, then can it say that *Indra* fighting with most of the enemies for water? The term *Dāsa* is mentioned here it shows that it was the war not only for cattle but for water also. If so then it raises a serious question on the theory of Rg Vedic society as pastoral dominated. But it would be haste to say that it was an agricultural society too. But there are some verses from the family mandala which can help us to understand the cause of the war for which Indra fought. It goes as:

पुरु यत्त इन्द्र सन्त्युक्त्वा गवे चकर्थावरासु युध्यन् ।

ततक्षे सूर्याय चिदोकसि स्वे वृषा समत्सु दासस्य नाम चित् ||[43]

Here Indra is fighting with Dāsa in the battle for shedding water on the fertile lands. So, if the interpretation of the passage is correct and Dāsa is identified with the non-Aryans then it would not be impossible that the Rg Vedic inter and intra-tribal war was not only for the cattle but also for the sake of water that might be used for irrigation purpose. Romila Thapar[44] rightly observes that the frequent reference to the *Indra- Vṛtra* conflict attempted to think that agriculture might be dependent on rainfall.

In other verses, Indra is called the owner of 'Kṣetra'. [45] In other verses, prayer is being made for the winning of land and water. [46] There is another verse from the family mandala which can be taken as conclusive evidence. Here is the dispute or battle fought for cattle, water and land. [47]

A.K. Yegna Narayan Aiyer believes that Rig Vedic people were well aware of irrigation through rivers which implies the construction of dams and laying out a canal irrigation system and they had the considered technical knowledge and skill. [48] R. N. Nandi argues that "Rg Vedic peasants used both drift irrigation and lift irrigation, the former through the channel (*khanitrimā*) connected with rivers and other water bodies and the latter with the help of pulley and suction. Pulley was used in the case of large, deep wells and suction in the case of masonry underground channels which ran for long distances, and water tapped wherever needed." [49] Besides that Wojtilla, who interprets the term 'Yavya' as stream or channel also offers the same view. [50] There are numerous passages where prayers are being made for diverting the course of water that either directly enters into cultivated fields or other water bodies like lakes or ponds. But the following passage makes it clear. It goes like this:

या आपो दिव्या उत वा स्रवन्ति खनित्रिमा उत वा याः स्वयञ्जाः।

समुद्रार्था याः शुचयः पावकास्ता आपो देवीरिह मामवन्तु ॥[51]

In the passage, the god Apah (water) is invoked by the poet for the water whether from the sky or through a channel being dug sprung up spontaneously may this divine water protect me. Wilson interprets the phrase '*Khanitrimā, khaṇanena nivṛttaḥ*' as either water stopped by digging, canals, or reservoirs in both cases water is used for irrigation purposes. A similar passage is from mandala second where *Indra* digs beds of rivers with his thunderbolt. [52]

So, the argument put forth by R. N. Nandi that Rig Vedic people knew the art of irrigation by drifting the course of river water seems correct. It is not sure whether they brought river water directly to their fields or store it in reservoirs like lake ponds or similar structures. This mechanism of water irrigation gives the reminiscence of Indus agriculture system. Possibly this system arose out of acculturation between Indo-Aryans and aboriginal people where they might have exchanged their ideas, knowledge, and experiences. J. Kuiper seems fairly right, after he found 300 non-Sanskrit works in RV, that it was a strong and high degree acculturation between non-Aryan agrarian populations which more or less integrated into a society of predominantly different character. [53] Allchin maintains that acculturation happened between Aryans and indigenous Harappan people and they influenced the Aryan language and culture. [54]

According to Romila Thapar, there was a symbiotic relationship of mutual dependence in which herder might graze their animals on the stubble of fields or be provided with fodder in return for protection and such agriculturist would then accept the authority of the herder chief without necessarily being conquered by them. [55] She takes its history back to Proto-state in Baluchistan in which the leading family of pastoralists becomes the focus of power and the settled agriculturalists are the source of wealth and labor. [56] But it is difficult to believe that the Aryan society retained their earlier way of life. The settled agriculture communities had already been established in many parts of India and Pakistan and these people survive and maintain their culture and language and influence the development of Indo-Aryan language and culture. [57] Besides that, the Rg Vedic people were very progressive and materialistic too. According to R. S. Sharma the hymns and verses of Rig Veda are concerned with material not spiritual well beings of people. [58]

The other evidence put forth, in support of the pastoral society, is that agriculture reference is scarce in the family mandala. There are only 21 references to agricultural activities in the RV but only a few occur in the family mandala. [59] It seems bizarre that since they applied a statistical approach to construct the Rg Vedic economy they overlook one simple fact. As we know that the RV is organized in 10 Mandalas, which contain 1028 *Śuktas* (hymns), consisting of 10552 mantras or verses. It would be pertinent to get aware of some basic facts. There are around 37% of the total hymns in

the text fall in the 1st [60] and 10th mandalas. On the other hand, the family mandalas (II to VII) consist of six mandalas and hold 41% of the total hymns. If we see it from another way then 59% of total hymns fall in the Mandala 1,8,9,10. So, it is natural that the higher the number of verses and hymns in the particular Mandala, the higher the possibility of occurring references regarding agriculture. This fact doesn't give much importance to historians or knowingly ignored it. It is said that the language of 1 and 10 mandala is refined and of later period but there is no consensus among scholars and linguists. B. K. Ghosh believes that the language of the first nine mandalas must be regarded as homogeneous.[61] R. S. Sharma quotes Hopkins, saying that the mandala IV of RV is among the latest of all family mandalas in which the hymn is devoted to agriculture operations.[62] But Talageri gives a different chronology of the family mandala of RV. According to him, Mandala IV is the oldest and the mandala V is the latest one.[63] Needless to say that there is much controversy over the chronology of R̥g Vedic Mandalas. So, this is important to avoid this controversial chronology of RV, especially of family mandalas.

R. N. Nandi rightly said that "The emphasis on a well-developed pastoral vocabulary and the comparative rarity of an agricultural terminology common to the earliest Indo-European speakers.... notwithstanding, the Rig Vedic language.... offers much more in the shape of terms for fertile plow lands, seed processing, surface drainage, tilling, sowing, reaping, winnowing, grain storing, corn-milling, flour-straining and so forth." [64]

It suggests that what is important is the agricultural process, tools, crops, and fertile lands that are mentioned in the family mandala rather than an emphasis on the numbers. Even if we go through the statistical data the term *Urvara*, which is generally interpreted as the fertile land, mentions nearly fifteen times in the text and occurs ten times in the family mandalas itself.[65]

Kṣtriya Śuktā[66] of the family mandala is the most important hymn which suggests that agriculture was an important aspect of the RV economy. In this hymn, *Kṣetrapati* is praying for the good yield of crops.[67] The most important facet of this hymn is that, in one of the verses, *Indra* is directly associated with agriculture. He is praying for holding the Sita(furrow) and Pusan to guide her.[68] The terms *Ṣuna* (plowshare), *Ṣira*(plough) are as gods. It should be remembered that in the later literature, *Indra* was as husband pati, of the furrow, Sita, or of the fallow field, *urvara-pati*. [69] So the tradition can be traced to the RV. Here *Indra* is actively participating in agricultural activities which suggests that R̥g Vedic Aryans gave much importance to farming too.

Although it's never easy to reach any conclusion that what exactly the nature of R̥g Vedic economy but it is certainly said from the above discussion that pastoralism and agriculture both played an important role in R̥g Vedic economy. The Apala hymn in which the possession of her father's head compared with his barren fields, clearly suggests the possibility of private property.[70] V.K. Thakur takes this hymn as conclusive evidence of the private property in RV. However, R. S. Sharma doesn't take it as conclusive evidence of the early R̥g Vedic period.[71] But a passage, from the family mandala, can be taken as conclusive if keep in mind that *Indra* is also called the *Urvarajit*. It goes like this:

विश्वजिते धनजिते स्वर्जिते सत्रजिते नृजित उर्वराजिते ।

अश्वजिते गोजिते अब्जिते भरेन्द्राय सोमं यजताय हर्यतम् ॥[72]

Here *Indra* is called the winner of land, cow, horse, etc. which shows that the fight was also for winning of land. This fact refutes R. S. Sharma's argument that *Indra* is not prayed for land although he admits that there is a fight for *Kshetra* (land) and interprets the term *Urvara* as fertile land.[73] If there was a fight for land then there is much possibility that they knew the private ownership of land. Although it is very difficult to know the true nature of land ownership whether it was clan or individual based.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that to construct the economic history of R̥g Vedic period it is important to make a subtle and comprehensive study of the text. Instead of statistical, it should be a contextual approach that can help to get a better picture of the Rig Vedic economy. It has been accepted by most historians who subscribe to the D. D. Kosambi and R. S. Sharma theory that R̥g Vedic people as nomadic one who roams around from one place to another place and *Indra* as their war god. It becomes necessary to raise a simple question why then R̥g a Vedic poet praying for rain or water and fighting for it? *Indra* played a dynamic role in the R̥g Vedic society. As the paper shows that He is praying for rain and also contested with enemies for the cause of water. Besides that, almost all Rig Vedic pantheons fight with the enemy of drought or might be real ones too.

It's not only *Vṛtra* but most of the demons were the cause of obstructing waters. Needless to say, those poets used their artistic skills and exaggerated the phenomena. Were all the wars and enemies mentioned in the Rig Veda mythical or there were some real ones also? In the later period, tribes like Koliya and Sakya fought over the distribution of river water that they used for their irrigation purposes. So, the possibility of war for the same cause can't be unexpected even in the Rig Vedic times. It should be kept in mind that *Indra* has also defeated *Dāsas*, who are supposed to be real enemies of Aryans, for the cause of water. This fact inclined us to conclude that the Rig Vedic people not only fight for cattle but for water also. And if the famous ten-king war happened for the cause of water as discussed in the paper, then undoubtedly agriculture also played a substantial role in the Rig Vedic economy.

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